

CAREX PACRISTYLIS

Annotation: the article presents data on the flora of Central Asia, especially the flora of Uzbekistan, sphenocaul plants growing in the arid steppes areas of Uzbekistan. The plant described is thick columnar sedge, or sward sedge, botany and physiology, economic and habitat features of the plant.

Key words: deserts, plains, steppes, river deltas, foothills, mountains, sward sedge, sedge plant, Asteraceae, legumes, grasses, Liliaceae, cruciferae, umbelliferae, hami-ly, buckwheat, alien, forage, reservoir. The vegetation of Central Asia is incredibly diverse and rich. Here, deserts and plains, steppes and river deltas, foothills and mountains form not only a peculiar landscape, but also determine the diversity of species. Few people know that a large number of plants grow in Central Asia. It may seem incredible, but in reality, compared with the central regions of Russia and even with the taiga, in the foothill and mountainous regions of Central Asia, the number of plants per unit area is many times greater. The total amount of vegetation, of course, is greater on the plains of many countries, but in terms of the overall diversity of species, Central Asia is ahead of many regions of the world. The richest flora of Central Asia includes more than 4,000 species of different plants. Plant communities are most strongly developed in foothill and mountainous regions. The main reason for the richness and diversity here is the altitudinal zonality of the relief, where each altitudinal zone is represented by its unique climate and weather conditions, soils, and different regions for the development of plants.

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In Central Asia, deserts, steppes and mountains connect side by side. In the deserts and steppes grows its own, special, adapted to the dry and hot climate of the vegetation cover. Tegal vegetation is widespread along the rivers and along the shores of lakes. In the mountains, the diversity is very large. Here you can distinguish several floras, each of which grows its own unique flora. At the same time, they talk about the so-called belt type of vegetation.

The complex topography of the mountains, its slopes with different exposures, facing different directions of the world, receiving a different portion of illumination, weathered and eroded with different intensity, have a strong influence on the distribution of various species. In addition, the composition of the soil, which directly depends on the steepness of the slopes and altitudinal zonality, also largely determines the diversity and diversity of the vegetation cover.

Uzbekistan is located in the center of Central Asia and is included in the arid (dry) zone of the Earth. The northern and western parts of Uzbekistan are occupied by the plains of the Taron lowland, the southern and eastern parts by the Tian Shan and Pamir-Alay mountain ranges. The landscapes of Uzbekistan are diverse: there are deserts, mountains, steppes, hilly-wood steppes in floodplains. Vegetation cover of Uzbekistan includes about 4280 species, 1628 genera from 178 families. Among them: 192 cultivated and cultivated plants from 79 families. About 577 wild-growing species are medicinal plants.

Compositae, legumes, cereals, labiales, cruciferae, umbellales, hana, lily, buckwheat, clover, horage, ranunculaceae are the richest in species in the flora of the republic. The complexity and unevenness of the relief determines the diversity of the vegetation cover. In Uzbekistan, five high-altitude fields can be distinguished, each of which has its own specific type of vegetation. Deserts and plains - "sahel", foothills and hills - "alya", mountains - "tan", highlands - "yaylan (yaylan)".

Sandy deserts (Most of the Kyzylkum desert, Samkhatl and Kattakum sands). In sandy deserts, species such as *Alypsan*, *caravel*, *salpe*, *sand acacia*, *Kilich's saltwort*, *antagalin*, *com-bearing com-bearing acacia*, *lute-toothed saffron*, and *haze* are common. Many of the plants have long roots, rhizomes, which prevent the mobility of sands in the desert.

We are conducting research work on the plant *thick-columnar sedge*, or simply *thick desert sedge*.

Thick-columnar sedge, or **Desert sedge** - *Carex pachystylis* - is a perennial herbaceous plant, a species of the genus *Sedge* (Carex), of the sedge family - Cyperaceae. It is an exceptionally valuable pasture forage with a high nutritional value. **Thick-columnar sedge** is an evergreen plant with a straight stem 1 to 30 cm long and a rhizome up to 6 cm long. The leaves are flat, shorter than the stems. Spikelets (1-6 pieces) crowded into a dense-flowered head.

SEEDS: with rhizomes

The plant is found in the Caucasus (Armenia), North Africa (Egypt), Western Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria,

Turkey), and in Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan).

It develops well on loamy, clayey and sandy loam soils. It is widely distributed in piedmont deserts, forming together with *bulbous bluegrass* (*Pha. bulbosa*) spheroidal pastures. In the absence of grazing or with moderate grazing, bluegrass displaces, and with excessive grazing, the dominance passes to bluegrass.

(NITROGEN-FREE EXTRACTIVE SUBSTANCES)

Phase	From absolute dry matter to %				
	ash	protein	fat	fiber	NFEI
Before flowering	9.0	22.0	5.3	93.0	43.0
Flowering	7.6	19.0	3.3	93.5	45.6
Fruiting	8.5	15.4	3.6	93.5	45.0
dry plant	8.2	8.4	2.6	93.6	51.2
wetted plant	96.2	7.5	2.3	94.6	45.4

For 100 kg of dry matter at the end of flowering, there are 102.1 feed units and 8.5 kg of digestible protein. Dry summer plants contain 51.7 feed units and 2.6 digestible protein.

The formation of a pillow by the Sedge plant

In Uzbekistan, and especially in the Bukhara region, wildcat sheep feed to build more in the steppe. Desert sedge is one of the best spring feed in the desert. In green and dry form, it is eaten by all kinds of farm animals and especially by horses and sheep. When eaten together with bluegrass, animals recover and gain fat after winter. Dry remains during the summer and winter are eaten ruminatively.

The plant tolerates moderate trampling well. In a favorable spring, after grazing, it can give 30-60% of the abundance of the original stock. In the city it is used as an ornamental plant.

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